

DigiAgro MLOps Questionnaire

Q1 This survey is part of a study on sustainable MLOps architecture at the Software Engineering and Architecture group of the University of Groningen. All responses are kept confidential and will only be reported on in aggregate form for the purpose of this study. Thank you for participating! Kind regards, Lech Bialek (l.w.bialek@rug.nl)

Q2 Which of the following describes best your role current role in your organization?

- Data Scientist (1)
- Software Engineer (2)
- ML Engineer (3)
- DevOps Engineer (4)
- MLOps Engineer (5)
- Solution Architect (6)
- Team Lead (7)
- Chief Technology Officer (CTO) (8)
- Other (please specify) (9) _____

Q3 How many years have you been working in this role?

- 0-2 (1)
- 3-5 (2)
- 6-10 (3)
- 11-15 (4)
- 16+ (5)

Q4 To what extent are you involved in the architecture or design of ML systems?

- Not involved (1)
- Occasionally consulted (2)
- Actively contributing (3)
- Primary decision-maker (4)

Q5 How many ML models are currently in production at your organization?

- 0 (Only experimenting) (1)
- 1-5 (2)
- 6-9 (3)
- 10+ (4)
- I prefer not to answer (5)

Q9 Definition of MLOps: The engineering practices enabling continuous integration and delivery of machine learning enabled software systems by means of version control, automation, monitoring and governance.

Q10 For each MLOps component below, please indicate the level of adoption in your organization:

	Already adopted (1)	Currently piloting (2)	Planned within the next 12 months (3)	Decided not to adopt (for now) (4)	Not Applicable in our use case (5)
Data collection (acquisition, loading) (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Data preprocessing (selection, cleaning) (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Data repository (raw data, data versioning) (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Code repository (training, deployment and application source code) (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Model repository (model versioning) (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Feature repository (store for reusable features) (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Metadata repository (experiment, training, performance metrics) (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Experimentation pipelines (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Model training pipelines (9)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Feature engineering pipelines (10)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Automated model (re)training (11)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Artifact repository (Containerized models) (21)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Automated model (re)deployment (12)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Fully automated MLOps operations (automated drift detection followed)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

by retraining and redeployment of model) (13)					
Inference engine/service (serving models) (14)	<input type="radio"/>				
Model monitoring (performance, model comparison, drift detection) (15)	<input type="radio"/>				
Retraining triggers (triggered by events, time interval or data/prediction drift) (16)	<input type="radio"/>				
Resources/container management (17)	<input type="radio"/>				
Orchestration (workflows, job scheduling, load balancing) (18)	<input type="radio"/>				
Logging and observability (19)	<input type="radio"/>				
MLOps dashboard/front-end (20)	<input type="radio"/>				

Q12 Please indicate how strongly the statements below influence the adoption of MLOps components at your organization:

	Strongly disagree (1)	Somewhat disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Somewhat agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)
MLOps can help reduce overall operational cost (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
MLOps provides a clear return on investment in the short-term (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
MLOps can help to scale down resources when demand is low to save cost (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
MLOps can reduce cost by quantization, pruning or compression (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
MLOps frameworks are well documented, maintained and receive regular updates (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
MLOps is compatible with existing software stacks (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
MLOps facilitates reproducibility and reproducible results (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
MLOps improves deployment reliability (zero-downtime, rollback) (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q13 Please indicate how strongly the statements below influence the adoption of MLOps components at your organization: (continued)

	Strongly disagree (1)	Somewhat disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Somewhat agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)
MLOps improves collaboration (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
MLOps helps to incorporate stakeholder feedback into model updates (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
MLOps improves fairness and explainability (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
MLOps eases compliance with privacy and AI regulations (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
MLOps improves resource efficiency (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
MLOps enables monitoring of energy consumption or carbon emissions (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
MLOps reduces model training / inference time (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
MLOps supports deployment on edge / local devices reducing data-center load (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>